

**AN ORIENTALIST READING OF COETZEE'S
FOE- A RECONSTRUCTION OF ROBINSON
CRUSOE**

By

Ayaz Ahmad Khan

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Ayaz Ahmad Khan

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Submitted By: AYAZ AHMAD KHAN
Name of Student

Registration #ML-PSC-FL16ENGBS-284

BACHELORS OF STUDIES IN ENGLISH LITERATURE AND LINGUISTICS (HONS)
Degree Name in Full

ENGLISH LINGUISTICS AND LITERATURE
Name of Discipline

Mr. Owais Ahmad

Supervisor

Mr. Islam Badshah

Chairman

Mr. Tariq Mahmood

Research Chairperson

Date

CANDIDATE DECLARATION FORM

I Ayaz Ahmad Khan

Son of Farin Khan

Registration #ML-PSC-FL16ENGBS-284

Discipline English Literature and Linguistics

Candidate of BS (HONS) ENGLISH at the National University of Modern Languages do hereby declare that the research article: AN ORIENTALIST READING OF COETZEE'S FOE- A RECONSTRUCTION OF ROBINSON CRUSOE submitted by me in partial fulfillment of BACHELOR OF STUDIES degree, is my original work, and has not been submitted or published earlier. I also solemnly declare that it shall not, in future, be submitted by me for obtaining any other degree from this or any other university or institution.

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

Chapter	Page
RESEARCH ARTICLE AND DEFENSE APPROVAL FORM	iii
CANDIDATE DECLARATION FORM	iv
ACKNOWLEDGMENT.....	v
DEDICATION	vi
TABLE OF CONTENTS.....	vii
ABSTRACT.....	viii
1 INTRODUCTION.....	1
1.1 Research objectives	5
1.2 Research Questions	5
1.3 Rationale	5
1.4 Significance of the study	5
1.5 Delimitation	6
2 LITERATURE REVIEWS	7
3 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY	10
3.1 Data Collection	10
3.2 Theoretical Framework	10
4 DISCUSSION	13
5 CONCLUSION	19
REFERENCES.....	21

ABSTRACT

This research study seeks to analyze an orientalist features in the novel, *Foe*. The analysis shows that in order to dig out the orientalist perspective, which have an immense importance in English Imperialism; Coetzee rereads and rewrites a celebrated and widely acclaimed novel of English Literature, 'Robinson Crusoe'. Coetzee, in 'Foe', takes the same characters from Defoe's *Robinson Crusoe* with slight changes in them, in order to show that how with the use of discourse one can construct anything, which on desires. The analysis examines the strategies of colonial masters through which they colonized and Orientalized the colonized countries. It also sheds light on the misrepresentation of the Orient by the Occident. It investigates the brutality of colonial masters and different tactics of colonizing the other countries during English colonialism.

Keywords: Edward Said, *Foe*, *Robinson Crusoe*, Reconstruction, Orientalism and Deconstruction.

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

J.M. Coetzee was born in Cape Town, in February 1940. Coetzee is an African born English novelist, essayist, linguist, translator, and receiver of Nobel Prize in 2003 in literature. His first novel is *Dusk-lands* (1974), he also wrote autobiographical novels like *Boyhood* (1997) and *Youth and Summertime* (2009).

The basic concern of Coetzee's works is Postcolonialism; '*Foe*' (1986) is one of them. It is basically the rewriting of a famous and widely praised novel of Daniel Defoe, known as *Robinson Crusoe* (1719). It is one of those canonical English novels which play a seminal part in colonizing the people (Said, 1978, P. 4-6). It presents a colonizer, Robinson Crusoe, as a hero. Defoe made him the representative of English middle class of the 18th century. Throughout the novel, Daniel Defoe used the character of Crusoe to construct the national identity of English people, and it greatly contributed in building the Euro-centrism, on the one hand, and British Imperial subjugation of people on the other.

Coetzee tries to reconstruct the famous celebrated English novel in a new way. Coetzee takes the same hero, as in Defoe's *Robinson Crusoe* (1719), but he portrays him in a different way in *Foe* (1986). Crusoe, in *Foe*, does not write journals about his adventurous life in on island, and this is done purposely by Coetzee; in order to reveal different ways of imperialism. Coetzee's *Foe* presents a different Crusoe; Crusoe is portrayed as irrational, savage, a typical Englishman, unreasonable, with such representation, Coetzee tends to convey two things; one is that how with the use of language one can construct anything and secondly, he deconstructs Defoe's Crusoe in *Foe* as while he is presented an ideal colonizer in *Robinson Crusoe*, which constructs Euro-centrism.

It is important to read Postcolonial texts in English to examine the responses to the perspectives held by the English authors, as gives a vivid picture of our historical actions created the world (Hawley, 2010). Let us consider the plot of novel *Robinson Crusoe* (1719), which is focused mainly on colonialism and the fabricated ideology of Englishness. The Postcolonial Coetzee's *Foe* (1986) deconstructs *Robinson Crusoe* and

exposes the lies, biasness, and injustices of English novelist, that are seen in Defoe's *Robinson Crusoe*. Coetzee picks a character Friday (who is without tongue) to speak out his heart, the confusion that who really cut out his tongue left unanswered. Susan, a female character tells Friday "your master says the slavers cut your tongue out; but I have never heard of such a practice. Is it the truth that your master cut it out himself and blamed the slave (Coetzee, 1986, P. 16)? The fact that this question is never answered, and that all attempts of Friday are failed to tell his story, this leaves the readers in a chaos whether the slavers that captured Friday removed his tongue, or that was done by the colonizer Cruso, who feels there is no need of great stocks of words; (Coetzee, 1986). This contradicts greatly with Defoe's *Crusoe*, who says: "I begun to keep my own journal; of which I shall give you the copy here, as long as it lasted; for having no more in, I was forced to leave it off" (Defoe, 1986). It shows clearly that Defoe's *Crusoe* gives great importance to language than Coetzee *Cruso*. And this is a colonial ploy, as with the use of discourse one can subjugate others (Said, 1978).

Robinson Crusoe is about Crusoe's adventurous experiences of life. He wishes to travel, to be rich, while his parents reject the idea. He ignores and begins to travel. On one such journey, his ship wrecks and Crusoe is the only survivor. He starts collecting the goods, from the already wrecked ship, and builds a small cave on island, and he starts writing a journal. In the meanwhile, he rescues a "cannibal", a black African native of the Island that Crusoe has landed on, and names him Friday, because Crusoe finds him on that day. Crusoe teaches Friday, how to use gun to kill a goat. When Friday refuses to use the gun, Crusoe is about to kill him but he thinks, "if I would let him, he would have worshipped me and my gun" (Defoe, 2010, p.260). Afterwards, Friday never defies and he starts worshiping Crusoe and his gun. Thus with the use of power Crusoe made Friday to be his subordinate. This is an instance of colonial subjugation of foreign lands.

Coetzee portrays Friday, in *Foe* (1986) without having his own tongue, in order to show that how the colonized people were used in the building of Euro-centrism. His novel, *Foe*, as an antithesis of Defoe's *Cruso*, exposes the biased approach of English novelist. While on the other hand Defoe's *Crusoe* colonized Friday by destroying his religion and language. He never asked Friday about his language but named him Friday and successfully ruined Friday's real identity. Crusoe taught English to Friday, and as time passes, Friday learns enough to talk to his master, Crusoe, at the end. Crusoe's

attempts to destroy Friday's language in a colonial play were successful. In Daniel Defoe's *Robinson Crusoe*, Crusoe asks Friday about his religion, but he does not bother to wait for Friday's response. Crusoe rejects his religion and tells him that his religion is superstitious and evil, and finally he is completely converted to Christianity. Crusoe gets succeeded in destroying the religious identity of Friday after destroying his cultural identity. Interestingly, Coetzee portrays Crusoe as an irrational, who rejects the idea of teaching to Friday, it conveys that with teaching and the imposition of name on Friday make him subordinate to his master, Crusoe. While Coetzee, on the other hand, avoid such approach to bring the ways of subjugation and misrepresentation into light.

In order to "civilize" Friday, Crusoe changed his ways of life, his manners of eating; he teaches him to eat milk and bread, instead of eating human's flesh as he is depicted as cannibal, who is fond of human flesh. In his colonial mind, Crusoe thought that he has changed him from being a cannibal into human being. Crusoe cooks goat's flesh for him in order to convert him from cannibalism, and Friday likes it so much, as Crusoe says, 'when he came to taste the flesh, he took so many ways to tell me, how he likes it, I couldn't but understand him' (Defoe, 2010, p.261) and Friday convinced Crusoe so much that he would not eat human flesh again. The civilizing mission of the colonial encounter carried out through their literature is visible in the novel.

Coetzee's *Foe* (1986) is a response to Defoe's *Robinson Crusoe*. It is the rewriting of *Robinson Crusoe* (1719) what Edward Said calls "contrapuntal" (Said, 1978, P, 51) reading of the English canonical texts to be able to reveal their inner prejudices and racism. J.M. Coetzee keeps the same characters in *Foe*. It is done purposely by Coetzee, in order to deconstruct them. Coetzee took the hero of Defoe's Robinson Crusoe and portrays him through his novel *Foe*, an embodiment of all that had gone unnoticed in reading English literary classics. Unlike what Defoe had done in *Robinson Crusoe*, Coetzee, in order to deconstruct him, shows him as superstitious, stupid, uncertain, pessimistic and evil in order to deconstruct Euro-Centrism. In *Foe*, Crusoe rejects the idea of writing journals, while in Robinson Crusoe he wrote about his experiences on the island that how English people colonized other people. Coetzee evinced the reality that white or English were not superior naturally rather they pretended to be, and therefore, Coetzee has deconstructed the self imposed nationality of superiority of Englishmen. Coetzee portrays Daniel Defoe as writer in the novel, *Foe*. Coetzee erases the "De" from his second name "Defoe" in order to show the

power of words, it suggests that with language and words, one can construct anything according to his desires. On the other hand, Friday, the slave of Crusoe in 'Robinson Crusoe', was used by Coetzee again as a slave of Crusoe in *Foe*. Friday could not speak as he is dumb. This thing symbolizes that in order to colonize people the white master took the language away from them.

Edward Said, a renowned postcolonial theorist, has done immense work in the development of Postcolonialism. His books *Orientalism* (1978) and *Culture and Imperialism* (1978) are considered to be path-breaking in many aspects. Edward Said explains that Orientals structured the world of two opposite phenomena: Us vs Them (Said, 1978, P, 2-6). Neither these distinctions are natural nor geographical but epistemological and ontological ones. The Orient has always been associated with lust, laziness, lack civility, while Occident is civilized and rational. Orientals developed a fantasized identity for non-European (Said, 1978, p.2) which was based on exactly those points that Coetzee highlights. The occident thought that Orientals could not take care of themselves, because they are lazy. The main concern of European researcher and visitors, Said tells us, was misrepresentation, to represent them: (p.1) "because they cannot represent themselves they must be represented" (Marx, 1818) The self-imposed superiority of Occident over Orient led Orientals and made them realize that they are competent and well enough to understand, interpret, and represent the stereotyped Orient. Thus, they started "Orientalizing" them and made them passive and subjective to the standards of West. According to Edward Said, "*Orientalism*" "was a discipline by which the Westerners were able to produce the Orient politically, economically, socially, ideologically, scientifically, imaginatively and sociologically. In short, due to Orientalism, Orient was not free at all, in terms of thought or actions, they had limitation over their thoughts and actions by Orientals" (p.3) Edward Said pointed out that the Orient was "imaginative geography" that the colonial masters not only produced but maintained as well. It was not something innate rather it was the power of discourse and hegemonic power (Said, 1978 p, 4). Or as Michale Gorra says in his wonderful book, *After Empire* that their strength was not that they were racially superior but because they had Martini rifles that allowed them to subjugate and colonize many countries and continents (1943, P, 55). The image was circulated so many times that something that was based on lies became a permanent marker of the colonized people. For Edward Said, *Orientalism* is a self-proclaimed projection, as a mirror for

the west to look who yearned to see themselves as superior, by describing the orient as inferior and uncivilized, in short, ‘‘Orient has helped to define West’’ (p.1).

1.1 Research objectives

- To find how does Coetzee unfold the ugly face of imperialism.
- To find out different aspects of Orientalist features.

1.3 Research Questions

- How does J.M Coetzee unfold the ugly face of imperialism in his novel, Foe?
- What are the different features of orientalism in Coetzee’s Foe?

1.3 Rationale

Many researchers and reviewers have explored J.M. Coetzee’s novel ‘Foe’ from various perspectives but it has not been explored from the perspective of ‘Orientalism’. After reviewing the literature, the researcher comes to find this gap which is to be filled. The rationale for this study is an attempt to analyze the text and find out different orientalist features to British Imperialism. The current study will enhance the knowledge of the future researchers, particularly related to this novel and the literature in general. The theory, which has been employed in this study, will contribute, in a great deal, to those who have a considerable association with English literature.

1.4 Significance of the study

This novel has been discussed by the different researchers and reviewers around the globe from multiple perspectives, but they have left out the space to describe it from postcolonial perspective specifically from Edward Said’s point of view. For this reason, this research study is of great importance to enhance knowledge of the English literature students, by providing them with knowledge related to this novel by describing from postcolonial perspective. The research thesis will definitely help to propagate the message of equality and tolerance by eliminating the evils of injustices and inequality.

1.5 Delimitation

Coetzee's 'Foe' (1986) is rich from researchers' perspective, but the researcher restricts this study to find allusions to the orientalist theory in the novel 'Foe' (1986), the researcher has chosen to dig out those allusions while applying postcolonial theory. Similarly, there are many theorists in the field of post colonialism, but the researcher has taken Edward Said's perspective. It has been limited to Edward Said's theory of post colonialism.

CHAPTER 2

LITERATURE REVIEWS

After in depth study of these articles, journals, and books to collect information about orientalism, binary opposition and contrapuntal approach, which involves re-reading of English texts, and how the orientals have remained passive, lazy, barbaric, savage, uncivilized, uneducated, lustful in English texts. It also explains that how with use of language European made the world of two opposing elements: civilized and uncivilized, Orient and Occident, educated and uneducated. However, all these articles have helped out the researcher to attain more knowledge about Post-colonialism in general and the biased approach of English novelists in particular. Similarly, the researcher has analyzed all these articles related to the research topic with the perspective of Orientalism and contrapuntal reading. Reviewing all the related literature has provided a gap for the current study that an orientalist study of Coetzee's *Foe*- a reconstruction of Daniel Defoe's *Robinson Crusoe*.

Azam N, (2018) states that Coetzee developed the scene recognizable from the beginning of the novel that Susan Barton, a female character in Coetzee's *Foe* (1986) never held the power, she has been powerless. He further argues Barton spent her whole life to keep men's wishes accordingly to keep them happy, to avoid confrontation, and to be accepted by the people. In the death scene of her king, she joined her master Cruso, death did not silence her at all, but her voice is inaudible since the novel began, though she shows she has power. On cursory level, Coetzee exposed to the reader; Barton is a strong female figure, character, she has always been shown on the pinpoint of struggle in order to publish her story. In all its profoundness it shows that she is not strong enough to face problems inside patriarchal society, she is still alive in colonial world, where men's dominancy exists and female being dominated. Finally, she is represented a postcolonial woman, a liberated woman, she wants freedom, she struggles for freedom. It concludes that Susan is not being controlled by male rather she herself chose to be silenced, in order to let the readers know that she favored being unheard.

Han w, (2017) states that novels present methodological sources sequentially to represent the nation- a fairy tale like identity. The most celebrated novel, *Robinson*

Crusoe was written in English literature where England circulated in the main setting. The novel, *Robinson Crusoe* portrays a colonizer an ideal English character, Robinson Crusoe which highlights the imaginative identity of England and establishes its national identity ‘Englishness’.

Defoe presented Robinson Crusoe as a lucky, rational, logical, strong, civilized and a God like figure, who possessed all good qualities of a strong man. By reading the English novel such like Robinson Crusoe, English people would come to make out themselves with Crusoe, they would always be considering themselves like him; a community, a nation superior to other, and the most civilized on the face of earth. On the contrary, in *Foe*, Coetzee undermined the boosted and imagined characteristics of Crusoe; he took the same Crusoe in *Foe*, and deconstructed him, by portraying him as foolish, sexually violent, and passive. He revisited Defoe’s Robinson Crusoe to be able to disclose to the readers that Euro-centrism was not innate rather it was an artificial. By converting Friday from Caribbean boy in Robinson Crusoe into a negro boy in *Foe*, to realize many things to African’s people; Africa as a community, black people are deprived from expression, how English destroyed Africa.

Neimneh S, (2014) explains the interaction between Post colonialism and feminism, with exceptional emphasis on silence and story-telling. The researcher examines it while analyzing the character of Barton and Friday. It states postcolonial ideology functions as the dominant woman one does; respectively, the racial and other. The researcher moved on to explain that as Friday has silenced it is just because of his race, he does not hold any access to power because of his race and color. On the other hand Barton has expelled from the center of authorship on her womanly growing; she was woman as well as ‘other’. The researcher concludes that Friday has no language, it is a reduction to colonized language; it shows a hole in which Coetzee resisted, at the end of the novel Susan gets her story told.

While to explain the self, language and history writing, Bunday G, (1998) argues that Coetzee takes Robinson Crusoe to wind down the conference of self, and history writing mirrors his views that Robinson Crusoe played an effective role in such things; as most of the critics observed in Defoe’s Robinson Crusoe one of the recurring characteristics of 18th century, free will, which works irrespectively of its setting. But

one the burning themes Coetzee have in *Foe* as an ant-thesis to challenge this premise of free will.

Coetzee challenges on which Robinson Crusoe dwells that language should be neutral, while history objective and self would be self-sufficient. Coetzee converts the dairy writer, control oriented, Crusoe into silent, passive and indifferent in *Foe*. Coetzee takes Roxana in the figure of Susan Barton as powerless woman seeking individualized selfhood. As 18th century male, Crusoe's individuality and power are substantial enough, where Susan desires to get rid of the state of powerlessness.

Language works as a skeletal stratum in the barren backdrop of *Foe*. While Defoe's Crusoe is compulsive and dairy writer, through that, Defoe tried to keep himself inside the battle of literary writing, as productive and constructive writer. While Coetzee's Cruso rejects dairy writing and speaking all together, while on opposite Susan considers writing story is the only way out to give reality, at the end, Coetzee uses Friday dumbness as an anti-thesis, as most of the character are silent only Susan tries to speak.

Peterson C, (2015) states that Susan continuously struggles to give voice to Friday which is founded on the claim of Cruso that Friday cannot speak because his tongue is cut out by his previous cruel slaves masters. In the meanwhile Susan does not prefer to look inside into Friday's mouth to know whether he has his tongue or not, when she is told to look by Cruso. This thing symbolically represents that she does never tried to verify that Friday does not possess tongue.

Throughout the novel Susan Barton tries to give voice to Friday, but she is repeatedly failed. It shows that Susan while having a narcissist she is unable and it became indispensable for her to get known to the Friday's inferiority. He argues that Susan fails due to the scarcity of linguistic, that how one can come to know other via traces they mark on us.

Many researchers have explored this novel from multiple perspectives, however, no one has explored it from Edward Said's perspective of post colonialism, and this research has conducted in order to fill that gap.

CHAPTER 3

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

While conducting this research study, the researcher has used qualitative research. This study involves textual analysis as it analyzes, in order to dig out different allusions to British Imperialism in Coetzee's 'Foe'. The researcher has investigated different allusions in J.M. Coetzee's novel *Foe* by employing Edward Said's concept of Orientalism.

3.1 Data Collection

The researcher has used two kinds of data collection sources, while conducting this research study; primary and secondary. As a primary data source the researcher has studied J.M Coetzee's novel, *Foe*. The researcher has used internet searches, studied different articles along with books, as a secondary source of data collection.

3.2 Theoretical Framework

While conducting this research study the researcher has applied Edward Said's concepts of "contrapuntal reading" of the canonical English texts and "Orientalism" presented in his groundbreaking books on postcolonial literary theory, *Orientalism* (1978) and *Culture and Imperialism* (1978). In order to bring to light different allusion in Coetzee's famous contrapuntal study of Daniel Defoe's canonical English text, *Robinson Crusoe* (1719), in his widely acclaimed novel *Foe* (1986).

Edward Said, the founder of postcolonial literary theory, in many respects, has left a remarkable array of concepts in his highly influential books, *Orientalism* and *Culture and Imperialism*. Both of his books pose as watershed in the literature of the marginalized, peripheral subjectivities and shed light on how the Orientals have been subjugated, colonized, and re-cast into a stereotypical mold where they are locked in a binary relationship with the Other: superior and inferior, master and slave, civilized and uncivilized. Said's work gives us an insight into how the colonizers were able to successfully colonize and subjugate the *other*. Said also shows how the Empire helped in its mission of subjugation by the literature, it produced called the canonical texts of

English Literature. Said shows how this helped them to build their own imaginative identity for English people.

The concept of Orientalism entails many things all at the same time. It means the construction of the Orient in a specific, rigid, immutable structure that deprives the Orient of its humanity. It demeans the plurality of cultures and people living in the Orient to be less significant than their colonial masters, hence a ripe case for a civilizing mission. In conceptualizing his opinion, Edward Said takes Michel Foucault's 'discourse' (1926) and complements it with the concept of hegemony that he borrows from Antonio Gramsci (1891). Discourse is defined as a situation where the powerful has the control of all propaganda machines as well as the military and territorial reach to silence a voice that disagrees with it. Foucault considered the power of Empire and the West in these terms. He believed that they have always painted white as good and black as bad for the simple reason that they had a control over the means of propaganda through which they controlled the truth. This control is called a discourse, where truth is silenced by elaborate lies. Edward Said thought that this is exactly what was happening to the Orient, Muslims, and Palestinians. They were painted as terrorists because America had access to Hollywood and media that they controlled. Muslims had no access so they were branded as terrorists. Said thought Foucault's concept is helpful in describing the situation in the Muslim world and about Islam and Muslims. Simply put, Foucault and Said opine that he who has knowledge has power.

He believes that one can be easily colonized mentally through the use of discourse. The history of the world is the truth of this truism. Orientalism is a self-proclaimed scheme of knowledge about the Orient, Edward Said believes, "which involves making statement about Orient and ruling over them" (p.6) This Orient was not basically what westerners shaped them in their books as lustful, lazy, irrational. He calls it imaginative territory that they created (p.4-5). This self-proclaimed scheme led many European scholars to think that they are the ones who understand orient better; therefore the orients were orientalized and were subjected to the superiority of west and to the standards of west which had not been what they appeared to be in their books. The main concern of European visitors was subjugation of the Orient on the one hand, and their representation of that subjugation, on the other: "they must be represented because they cannot represent themselves," as Said quotes Karl Marx on the

first page of *Orientalism*. The self-proclaimed projection of Orientalism underwent many scholars who took a biased and selective approach in the representation of Orients; it is what Edward Said calls western cultural discourse. (P, 25)

The only out way to these biases and artificial and imagined divisions' between orient and occident, Edward Said believes, is contrapuntal approach (Culture and Imperialism, 1978, p, 51-53). He offers it to scholar to adopt this approach as a "simultaneous awareness" of metropolitan and "other" culture. This concept of contrapuntal can be applied in reading, interpreting and revisiting English texts in order to take out the ideological biases and to know how a dominating discourse acts, (p, 51) as they shape English nationalism and imperialism, and how a new counter-narrative can be developed. The identities of the Orient are not something God given rather, as Said shows, the result of colonialism through the discourse of Orientalism. Edward Said argues that English text needs to be reread, reviewed and re-written with a consideration for the interdependence of past and present. They must emphasize on the relationship between Empire, culture and text.

This study is an attempt to deeply evaluate different allusions in Coetzee's novel, *Foe*, by making use of Edward Said's concept of contrapuntal approach. The researcher has studied the novel thoroughly and focuses on the different uses of allusions to British Imperialism and how Coetzee attempts to re-read Daniel Defoe's novel Robinson Crusoe.

CHAPTER 4

DISCUSSION

J.M. Coetzee's *Foe* (1986) is a counter attack on Defoe's *Robinson Crusoe* (1719), Coetzee adopted Edward Said's concept of contrapuntal approach, thus, he re-writes Defoe's *Robinson Crusoe*, in order to reveal the truth.

As far as the meaning of the title, 'Foe', is concerned, *Foe* means an 'enemy' and 'false'. Enemy, which symbolically refers to the well-known English novelist Daniel Defoe, where Coetzee erases his original name and portrays him as 'Foe' in order to deconstruct, and to show that how with words, one can construct anything. By changing Daniel Defoe's original name into *Foe*, which means an enemy, Coetzee indirectly refers that colonizer is the enemy.

Another possible meaning of *Foe* can be 'false', it refers to an English novel, '*Robinson Crusoe*', as a 'false' tale, which is beyond reality. While, in order to recognize the truth, Coetzee used contrapuntal reading. As there is a circulated debate in Coetzee's novel *Foe* on the account of Friday's silence. 'The slavers cut out his tongue and sold him into slavery, the slave hunters of Africa. But surely he was a mere child when they took him. Why would they cut out a child's tongue?' (Coetzee, 1986, p. 13)

In Defoe's '*Robinson Crusoe*', Crusoe the English master, rescues what he calls cannibal and names him Friday, because he is found on that day, without asking Friday's native language; Crusoe imposes his own language on Friday, eventually Crusoe colonized him by taking his language and make him a slave. He teaches him English language for his own benefit, 'Friday begun to talk and understand the names of almost anything' (Defoe, 1719, pp. 260-265). Thus Coetzee, in *Foe*, presents Friday to be deprived of a tongue, he tries to reveal the ugly face of British imperialism. In order to impose European civilization, Defoe adopted the technique to remove the language; in that case he is the *Foe*, an enemy, and his novel *Robinson Crusoe* is false, along with the imposition of language on Friday.

I am growing to understand why you want Crusoe to have a musket and he besiege by cannibals. I thought it was a sign you had no regard of truth. I forgot you are a writer

who knows above all how many words can be sucked from a cannibal feast, how few from the wind. It is all a matter of words and the number of words, is it not? (Coetzee, 1986, p. 60-61)

From the above mentioned lines, which have been taken from the original text, Susan Barton, a female character in the novel, who wants to publish her story of an Island, she writes to Mr. Foe, a character in the novel, to publish her story, but she says, "why should a man endeavor to save a musket when he is unable to save his own life?" (Coetzee, 1986, P. 33)

Foe wants her to mention Crusoe with guns and be besieged by cannibals, as her story is conditioned to it. But she admits the truth, "what I saw, I wrote, I saw no cannibals." (Coetzee, 1986, P. 33) As it was Defoe's strategy to implement Western civilization and superiority on the island to have guns.

In Defoe's Robinson Crusoe, Crusoe taught Friday to use gun, when Friday defied because he was afraid of guns, Crusoe threatened him and wanted to kill him, but he mediated "if I would let him leave, he would have worshiped me and my gun" (Defoe, 1719, pp. 259-260). Friday never rebels against Crusoe and starts worshiping Crusoe and his gun; therefore with armed force, Crusoe colonized Friday and he became his subordinate. While in Foe, Crusoe does not wish to keep guns, here Coetzee is referring to British way of colonizing the people with guns. He suggests that they made slaves and colonized the people because they have power- guns, which is termed by Edward Said as hegemony. As Robinson started colonizing people who were wild, lustful, barbarian who were represented by Friday. Crusoe scars Friday with gun and Bible which were the ways of colonizing.

Another recurring allusion to British Imperialism can be seen in Crusoe, a white master in the novel Foe and at the same time in Defoe's Robinson Crusoe. There's a link between Empire and Defoe's Robinson Crusoe, as Crusoe is shown as a god like figure, rational, self-obsessed, determined, civilized, educated, and competent in Robinson Crusoe, who worked alone on a deserted Island to survive and to colonize. Therefore, whenever English people read this novel, they identify themselves with Crusoe, which encouraged people how to rule the world and how to colonize people. Robinson Crusoe constructed an imaginative identity of "Englishness" for Europeans in order to show that they are superior to the rest of the world.

I turned and saw Crusoe's wild hair and the great beard he never cut and his yellow eyes, and I knew it was all true, I was indeed castaway on an island with a man named Cruso, who though an Englishman was as stranger as a Laplander. I pushed his hands away and made to rise, but he held me. No doubt I have freed myself, for I was stronger than he. But I thought, he has not known a woman for fifteen years, why would he not have his desires? (Coetzee, 1986, P. 18)

In contrast, as the above lines show, Coetzee took the same character with slight changes in his name, as Cruso from Robinson Crusoe, and makes changes in his behavior. In order to deconstruct his imaginative identity, Coetzee came up with Foe as an anti-thesis of Robinson Crusoe. He portrayed him as wild, irrational, superstitious, in order to deconstruct him, his reason, and Euro-centrism portrayed by Defoe's Robinson Crusoe, it contributed in the construction of "'Englishness'", which has been deconstructed by Coetzee in 'Foe' by adopting Said's contrapuntal approach to canonical texts like *Robinson Crusoe*.

As Crusoe is no longer standing firm on sure ground, as he was in Defoe's Robinson Crusoe but a different one depicted by J.M Coetzee as Foe and tells the truth about their colonial tales of adventure.

"The African slavers cut out tongue and sold him into slavery." (Coetzee, 1986, P. 18)

Friday's silence can be another allusion to British Imperialism. Defoe used this character in Robinson Crusoe to unveil the themes of subjugation, identity, the concept of slavery and oppression. In order to colonize people, Crusoe in Robinson Crusoe taught Friday his own language, without asking Friday's native language and named him Friday, as he was found on that day. So, Defoe's way of colonization was to destroy the language and substitute it with his own one. As in Robinson Crusoe, Crusoe takes pleasure in teaching English to Friday, in this way; it improvises the notion that Crusoe gave him language. "The African slavers cut his tongue and sold him into slavery". (Coetzee, 1986, p. 13)

On the contrary, Coetzee challenged Defoe, he uses the same character Friday in Foe, although, he portrays him in different way than Defoe, he introduces Friday, having no tongue in 'Foe', a slave who could not speak. He basically seems to suggest that we should not give voice to those who could not speak, to stand by himself, as

Susan Barton says: The only tongue that can tell Friday's story is the tongue he has lost (Coetzee, 1986 P. 42) *Coetzee's* Crusoe rejects to teach Friday, "Cruso would not teach Friday because he said, Friday had no needs of words". (Coetzee, 1986, P. 35)

On the other hand, Crusoe in 'Robinson Crusoe' deconstructs Friday's history and culture by teaching him his own habits of eating, thereby, in his thought, converting him from cannibalism; teaching him to eat goat's flesh. Defoe claims that it was right for Crusoe to hold the position of master and teach to Friday, in order to subjugate him. Postcolonialism challenges these presuppositions. For example, in Chinua Achebe's novel, *Things Fall Apart*, Achebe shows how things that were together and well-knit were torn apart by a stupid Englishman, who claimed to teach cannibals their manners. They destroyed the societies because they were racist. They thought whiteness was something superior in comparison to darkness, which they also thought to be uncivilized. Postcolonialism contests this construction of the world. It uses the findings in social and human sciences in the west, like in psychology, political science, and philosophy, to make their point. Said, for instance, takes Foucault and Gramsci from this new pool of knowledge, to construct his conception of *Orientalism*, which inspired Bhabha and Spivak too. Postcolonialism, therefore, is a viable argument to deconstruct colonial legacies.

Coetzee is contrapuntally reading Daniel Defoe to reveal the ideological bias of the writer. He shows how Defoe depicts Africans the way they are treated by them on the ground as colonial masters. They have withheld language, culture, and civilization from people, as they consider them inferior on account of their skin color. This is exactly the point that Edward Said is making in *Orientalism* that it is based on utter racism and is premised upon their Martini rifles not the superiority of their culture or civilization. "I begun to keep my journal, of which I shall here give you the copy" (Defoe, 1917, P. 44).

Defoe's Crusoe prefers keeping journals of adventurous journeys and experiences of an island in order to write stories and history of his journey. It is his way of telling English people to be colonizer by nature and nation. It would convey the idea of "east is east and west is west" (white Men's burden, 1899)

"Cruso kept no journals, perhaps he lacked paper and ink but more likely, I now believe, because he lacked the inclination to keep one, or if he ever possessed the

inclination he had lost it.” (Coetzee, 1986, p. 9) While Coetzee’s *Crusoe* prefers keeping no journals he says “I will leave behind my terraces and walls. They will be more enough.” (P, 10)

Coetzee challenges the imaginative identity of superiority of Europeans by deconstructing what Defoe has constructed with writing. He tells that the superiority of Europe to other countries was not innate rather it was constructed through writing.

Language, in Defoe’s *Robinson Crusoe*, plays an important role in subjugating and colonizing the other, it also stands as cornerstone in the construction of imaginative national identity of ‘Englishness’. As *Crusoe* speaks English, who is shown as a strong, rational, and god-like figure, hence, people around the world who spoke the same language identify themselves with him as a superior to others. It is language through which Defoe utilized to build his identity. Defoe’s ways of colonization were to erase the language, and we see this when *Crusoe*, in ‘*Robinson Crusoe*’, named a slave Friday without investigating his culture. He also starts teaching him English without asking about Friday’s language, he converts the habits of “cannibal” and teach him to eat goat’s flesh. Eventually, with the use of language, Defoe portrays Englishmen as rational, strong, civilized and educated. However subjugate Friday to *Crusoe* by portraying him as cannibal, who eats human’s flesh.

On the other hand, Coetzee gave his novel a title ‘Foe’, by erasing Daniel Defoe’s original name to Foe, in order to show that with language one can make anything. “your pen, your ink” (Coetzee, 1986) “but they transfer to me when I write”. He purposely introduced Friday in ‘Foe without having tongue’, it literally exposes that how colonial master treated the people. How they had been shown to the world; as inferior, barbarian and uncivilized. Coetzee deconstructed it and revealed the injustices and lies of Defoe’s *Robinson Crusoe*.

Coetzee converted Friday as a Caribbean cannibal from Defoe’s *Robinson Crusoe* to a Negro boy in *Foe*. In *Foe* when Susan Barton wants her story of island to be published, she repeatedly sends letters to Mr. Foe to publish her story, but when he asks her to mention cannibals in the story. She says, in response, “what I saw, I wrote, I saw no cannibals.” (*Foe*, 1986 P, 14). Coetzee adopts contrapuntal approach, in order to reveal the false and fantasized foundation of Defoe’s *Crusoe*.

In Defoe's *Robinson Crusoe*, when the ship is wrecked and only Crusoe became the only savior, at first he could not face hardships, but he then used his reason and fetched the tools in order to adopt living in, such as clothes, gun, and food.

The ship lies on the bed of the ocean, broken by the waves and covered in sand, what has survived the salts and sea-worm will not be worth saving. We have a roof over our heads, made without saw and axe. We sleep, we eat, and we live. We have no needs of tools. (Coetzee 1986, p. 19)

As the above lines show, they have been taken from 'Foe'; Coetzee's Crusoe rejects to have tools and muskets from the ship, because he can make living without them. It puts a mark that Defoe's Crusoe picked up guns from the wrecked ship to protect him against the cannibals and to force people to be his slave by using his gun. Coetzee reveals that one of Defoe's ways of creating slaves, and colonizing people was armed forces.

Plantation of seeds to occupy the blank spaces can be another allusion to British way of Imperialism. In Defoe's *Robinson Crusoe*, Crusoe colonized the deserted island. The island in which he was adopted to live, were blank spaces, deserted, passive and primitive. He started civilizing them by cultivation. He sow seeds to grow wheat in order to make living, he colonized the animals and kept them for milk.

If your master had truly wished to be a colonist and leave behind a colony, would he not have been better advised to plant his seeds in the only womb there was? The farther journey from his terraces, the less they seem to me like fields waiting to be planted. (Coetzee, 1986, p. 53)

As the above lines show, Coetzee's Crusoe left a colony behind without planting seeds on the island. Coetzee reveals that it was the way of British Empire of colonialism. They planted the blank spaces with seeds and colonized them, as Defoe's Crusoe did. As Mr. Foe says, in Foe, "if you ever planted a seed, that progress enough". (P, 96).

CHAPTER 5

CONCLUSION

“Your pen your ink, but they become mine when I write.” (Coetzee, 1940)

After analyzing J.M Coetzee’s novel, *Foe*, the researcher finds some allusion to British imperialism. Coetzee reveals these allusions via contrapuntal reading. He shows that how an iconic English author, Daniel Defoe followed a selective and biased approach in the representation of the orient. In order to show that how language stands as a corner stone in colonization; Coetzee exposed that how English imperialists tried to represent the orient, by taking the language from them and replaced it with their own, as depicted by Coetzee through a character Friday, who does not have his own tongue. In Defoe’s *Robinson Crusoe*, Friday’s identity was completely deconstructed, he was taught English language without taking his own identity into consideration, his manners and habits were replaced with English ones. Coetzee evinced these things in ‘*Foe*’ as he portrayed Friday as dumb and his English is cut out by the slave owners.

Coetzee portrays the well known English novelist in novel as an author and named him *Foe*; to show that how with language one can construct anything. In the same way he entitles his novel, ‘‘*Foe*’’. *Foe* symbolically refers to an English novelist Denial Defoe, that he is the enemy.

At another place the researcher has observed an English ideal hero *Robinson Crusoe*, who is shown in a novel, named *Robinson Crusoe* as a rational, reasonable, strong, civilized and educated, but is completely deconstructed and subverted in *Foe* by Coetzee. Coetzee’s *Cruso* rejects keeping journals, which was Defoe’s strategy of imperialism, besides he does not sow seeds to fill the blank spaces, where Defoe’s *Crusoe* sow seeds to make his survival possible on the island and he occupies it. Similarly, Coetzee’s *Cruso* rejects Susan Barton’s contention that why *Cruso* does not teach to Friday, in response *Cruso* tells her that Friday does not need to be taught, *Cruso* does not want him to be his subordinate. When Susan wants to get her story published, *Foe* tells her that she needs to mention that *Cruso* is being besieged by cannibals. But she says that she saw no cannibals on island.

Foe investigates Susan, when she wants her story published, that why Crusoe does not pick tools and muskets from the wrecked ship, he suggests Susan to mention in her story that Crusoe picked up tools and guns from the ship, but she does not do it, she says that what she had seen, she has written. While Defoe's Crusoe picks up tools and guns long with clothes in order to protect him from the cannibals, and with gun, language, and religion, he subjugated Friday to be his subordinate.

In Defoe's Robinson Crusoe, Crusoe represents Friday with his own language; he teaches him English and replaced his language with English. On the contrary, Coetzee in his novel, Foe portrays Friday without having tongue, but as Susan story does not get published because she says that the story of Friday can be told by the tongue, he has lost. So here Coetzee does not represent him in order to reveal the injustices of English imperialism, also to show the misrepresentation of English novelists.

However, different allusions in 'Foe' has been explored in this research study. The study was conducted in the light of textual analysis, all the text of the novel has been deeply interpreted to dig out the allusions. There are some other aspects in the novel, 'Foe' which have not been explored yet. Therefore, the researcher suggests the future researchers to explore it from the perspective of postmodernism.

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